

Call 1 report on dissemination activities

31 January 2025

Document identifier: D3.3

Version: 2

Authors: Ona Tribó, Jordi Malapeira, Sònia Sánchez.

Dissemination status: Public

Co-funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101126533.

D3.3 CALL 1 REPORT ON DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Grant Agreement n°:	101126533
Project acronym:	TOUCH
Project title:	Towards the next generatiOn of excellent yoUng doctoral researchers on mental health by developing an intersectoral & transdisciplinary approaCH
Funding Scheme:	MSCA-COFUND-2022 (DOCTORAL PROGRAMME)
Project Duration:	2024/02/01 – 2029/01/31 (60 months)
Beneficiary:	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)
Implementing partners:	Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics (CED) Centre de Recerca Matemàtica (CRM) Centre de Visió per Computador (CVC) Fundació Salut i Envel·liment (FSIE) Institut d'Investigació i Innovació Parc Taulí (I3PT) Institut de Recerca Sant Pau (IR Sant Pau) Vall d'Hebron Institut de Recerca (VHIR)

Project no. 101126533

TOUCH

Towards the next generatiOn of excellent yoUng doctoral researchers on mental health by developing an intersectoral & transdisciplinary approaCH

MSCA-COFUND-2022 (DOCTORAL PROGRAMME)

Start date of project: 01/02/2024 Duration: 60 months

History Chart				
Issue	Date	Changed page(s)	Cause of change	Implemented by
1.0	13/1/2025	-	Draft	PRUAB
2.0	20/1/2025	-	Version 2.0	UAB

Validation			
No.	Action	Beneficiary	Date
1	Prepared	UAB	13 January 2025
2	Approved	UAB	21 January 2025
3	Released	UAB	25 January 2025

Disclaimer

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of contents

D3.3 CALL 1 REPORT ON DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES.....	1
1. Report on dissemination activities	4
1.1. TOUCH website.....	4
1.2. Social media	5
1.3. TOUCH Info Day	6
1.4. Email campaign	7
1.5. EURAXESS	8

1. Report on dissemination activities

1.1. Website

During the first months of the TOUCH, we focused on the creation of the [website](#). The web is in English and it has an attractive design and a clear structure to help users navigate. It was launched on **1st of March of 2024** and it has been regularly updated.

The website is the main channel of the programme and contains the most important information, such as the description of the doctoral programme, the participating organisations, information on open calls, the guide for applicants, FAQs and helpdesk information.

Website Analytics (February 2024 – December 2024)	
Nº of sessions	19.705
Nº of users	8.652
Nº page views	58.151
Nº of pages per user	1,4
Avg. session duration	1 min 56 s

1.2. Social media

Social media is also an important channel for engagement and participation that complements the website. We have not created specific profiles for the programme on social networks, as the participating organisations have their own profiles with a high impact. For this reason, it was decided to promote the programme through their profiles on X, LinkedIn and Instagram, using the hashtag [#TOUCHprogramme](#) [#MSCA](#) and banners announcing the call.

	X	LinkedIn	Instagram
Posts	26	17	5
Impressions	24.830	295.320	1.267

1.3. Info Day

The **TOUCH Info Day**, a virtual event tailored for potential doctoral candidates, took place on 30 April 2024. The aim of the event was to present the various opportunities offered by the TOUCH doctoral programme and to provide detailed information on the first call for applications.

The two-hour event started at 10:00 CEST and consisted of two parts. The first was a comprehensive presentation of the programme by the project manager, followed by an interactive second part where potential applicants could ask questions.

The Info Day video uploaded on Youtube:

<https://youtu.be/qGANLojYCjA?si=UpubqyYRqXoGd2Q5>

TOUCH Info Day	
Nº of registrations	150
Nº of participants	75
Nº questions by attendees	31
Nº views of the uploaded video	249

1.4. Email campaign

During this first period, communication efforts focused on the dissemination of the first call. The aim was to attract as many international applicants as possible, so we ran a **digital communication campaign**. We sent an [email campaign](#) with the main information of the first call and the Touch Info Day to relevant mental health associations & networks as well as to the broad international network of partners and EU projects on the topic of the programme. In addition, a [news](#) item was published on all the project partners' websites.

Email campaign	
Total opens	859
Total clicks	106

UAB Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

1st call of TOUCH doctoral programme

Towards the next generation of excellent young doctoral researchers on mental health by developing an intersectoral & transdisciplinary approach

TOUCH Mental health & wellbeing
FIRST OPEN CALL
13 doctoral positions

TOUCH is a new excellent doctoral programme led by the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) for the recruitment and training of **24 doctoral researchers** in the field of mental health and wellbeing.

The first call opens from 1 April to 30 June offering 13 doctoral positions under four major thematic areas:

- Fostering mental health and wellbeing across lifespan
- Transdisciplinary approach to mental health & wellbeing determinants
- Multilevel strategies for assessment and intervention in mental health & wellbeing: from genomics to personomics
- Governance in mental health systems: participation, education, and community personomics

What does TOUCH offer?

- Over **30 opportunities** to undertake research projects with renowned supervisors.
- 3-year full-time contract** (37.5 hours / week) and a gross salary of **2.375 €/month** (the salary will be the same for the 3 years)
- The availability of world-class **research infrastructures**
- An excellent training programme**, including practical hands-on schools, training in research diversity and scientific and communication skills, international and/or intersectoral secondments at partner laboratories and premises.

Join the TOUCH Info Day

Join us on 30 April 2024 for the **TOUCH Info Day**, an online session for doctoral candidates to explore the opportunities provided by the TOUCH doctoral program. Learn more about the call and get answers to your questions about the application process.

TOUCH
Online Info Day
30 April 2024 | 10:00 h CEST
Register now >

Co-funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 10120553.

1.5. EURAXESS

The TOUCH programme job opportunities were announced on the EURAXESS website on 15 March 2024. The publication provided comprehensive information for potential candidates to apply for the available positions. It included a detailed description of the predoctoral programme, research and training activities, partner institutions, eligibility criteria, employment conditions, and the selection process. Additionally, clear and precise instructions were provided for submitting applications through the TOUCH website. The job advertisement remains accessible at the following link to the [EURAXESS platform post](#).

The screenshot shows the EURAXESS website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the EURAXESS logo and a 'Log in' button. Below the navigation bar, the breadcrumb trail reads 'Home > Jobs & Funding >'. The main heading of the page is '13 PhD positions on mental health and wellbeing in the framework of the TOUCH COFUND project led by the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona'. On the left side, there is a 'PAGE CONTENTS' menu with links for 'Job Information', 'Offer Description', 'Requirements', 'Additional Information', 'Work Location(s)', 'Where to apply', and 'Contact'. The 'Job Information' section is expanded, showing details for the job posted on 15 MAR 2024. The job information includes the following details:

Organisation/Company	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)
Research Field	Psychological sciences Biological sciences Neurosciences Demography Sociology Medical sciences Computer science
Researcher Profile	First Stage Researcher (R1)
Country	Spain
Application Deadline	30 Jun 2024 - 23:59 (Europe/Madrid)
Type of Contract	Temporary
Job Status	Full-time
Is the job funded through the EU Research Framework Programme?	H2020 / Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions COFUND
Marie Curie Grant Agreement Number	101126530
Is the Job related to staff position within a Research Infrastructure?	No

In addition to the general TOUCH programme announcement, each of the 34 projects offered in the first call was published individually on the EURAXESS portal. These individual postings included not only the general programme information but also a detailed description of the specific research project, supervisors, research group, and the required skills and qualifications for a competitive application. The links to the individual publications were provided in the deliverable D3.1.